

Deliverable 6.3

1st Dissemination, Communication and Networking Activities

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1st Dissemination, Communication and Networking Activities

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Executive summary

This deliverable describes the communication, dissemination, and networking activities carried out during the first 18 months of the FoSSNet project (February 2024 – July 2025), in line with the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan outlined in Deliverable D6.1 and under Work Package 6: *Creating Impact*.

Key activities included the development of the project website, social media engagement, media outreach, production of communication materials, and collaborative communication initiatives with other networks and projects. These efforts aimed to raise awareness, build the project's identity, and engage stakeholders, with progress assessed based on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in D6.1.

The report follows a similar structure to the DEC Plan, detailing all activities and materials produced so far and concludes with a section mentioning next steps as the project moves into its next phase, focusing on deeper stakeholder engagement and preparation for long-term impact.

Overall, considering the project's developments and results obtained so far (as shown by the KPIs, in chapter 5), a few adjustments were introduced to the initial strategy and are summarised in the table below:

Change	Chapter	Explanation
Update of the C&D tools and activities	Chapter 4	The description of tools and activities was updated according to the results achieved, and new tools (e.g. project newsletter) were added to support the project's activities in place and increase both their reach and impact.
Update of the KPIs	Chapter 5	Results obtained until July 2025 were added, as well as clarifications regarding some of the KPIs.
Revision of the management process	Chapter 6	Some adjustments were made, namely those related to reporting activities and monitoring (to be included in the internal newsletter every 3 months).

Update of the next steps	Chapter 7	The chapter contains an overview of the scope of the activities for the following period of the project.
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A crucial opportunity to assess and further plan the upcoming activities will be the feedback and recommendations from the European Commission's independent reviewers, expected as part of the first interim evaluation report in October 2025. This will also guide the refinement of the communication and dissemination strategy.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EUFIC	European Food Information Council
FSS	Food Systems Science
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
RUC	Roskilde University
SFSN	Sustainable Food Systems Network
SNA	Social Network Analysis
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

FoSSNet aims to establish a long-lasting pan-European academic network for Food Systems Science (FSS), advancing open and inclusive science and education to address the demand for a sustainable transformation. By enhancing and deepening academic networks, FoSSNet seeks to establish an improved Knowledge & Innovation governance structure capable of meeting the emerging challenges of ensuring Europe's nourishment in a healthy, sustainable, and fair manner. FoSSNet's transdisciplinary, inclusive and systemic approach will support the integration of various disciplines and enhance connections and cooperation among food systems scientists, driving collaborative solutions for food systems transformation.

Communication and dissemination activities are essential components of the FoSSNet project, supporting its ambition to create impact and ensure the project's visibility, engagement, and long-term sustainability. This document provides an overview of the communication, dissemination, and networking activities carried out since the start of the project in February 2024 to July 2025. These activities have been implemented in line with the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan outlined in deliverable D6.1 (submitted in M6, July 2024).

The following chapters will highlight the progress made in raising awareness about FoSSNet, establishing a recognizable project identity, and initiating stakeholder engagement. In addition, this document includes updates to the initial communication and dissemination strategy, based on the experience and results achieved so far, assessed by the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in D6.1.

The deliverable is organised to reflect a similar structure to the original DEC Plan (D6.1), starting with a chapter addressing the target audiences and messages, followed by a chapter dedicated to the FoSSNet vision and mission. The subsequent chapters describe the communication channels and tools, such as the project website, social media presence, media outreach, digital and printed materials, and collaborative communication initiatives with other networks and projects. The final section of the document will present an overview of the updates integrated at this stage and the next steps for the subsequent period of the project.

The activities outlined here are part of the broader communication and dissemination strategy that will continue to evolve over the course of the project. Two further reports on communication, dissemination, and networking activities are planned for months 36 and 48, respectively. This deliverable not only highlights the progress made during the first 18 months, but also sets the stage for the next phase of the project focused on

mobilising a wider range of stakeholders to engage in the project (for instance, through the Territorial Labs, the Knowledge Hub, Winter/Summer Schools) and to make use of its resources, highlighting benefits and addressing specific knowledge needs.

1.1 Objective and scope

The aim of the communication and dissemination actions in FoSSNet is to ensure that the project's objectives and results are effectively communicated, thereby maximising the project's impact by reaching all relevant target audiences.

This report serves as an overview of the project's communication, dissemination and networking actions during the first 18 months of FoSSNet, along with their outcomes.

2 Target audiences

In the DEC Plan (D6.1), EUFIC, in collaboration with all FoSSNet consortium members, identified the actors that will interact with the project throughout its course, and defined the objectives of these interactions and streams of engagement.

FoSSNet's communication activities have been targeting the following audiences:

- Research performers
- Early career researchers and educators
- Students in Higher Education
- Research and Academy Leadership
- Policymakers, their agencies and research-policy initiatives at several levels
- Existing networks of scientists and science institutions
- Living labs
- EU/national publicly funded projects
- Food systems organisations and networks
- Investors

The DEC Plan (D6.1) also includes a detailed analysis of all target audiences listed describing who they are, what subgroups belong to each audience, how they will be addressed by FoSSNet activities, and the key messages intended for each group.

In this section, we highlight the main audiences targeted during this first 18 months of the project, along with the focus of the messages delivered.

The main audiences engaged so far include:

- Research performers;
- Research and Academy Leadership;
- Existing networks of scientists and science institutions;
- EU/national publicly funded projects;
- Early career researchers, educators
- Students in higher education

Efforts to continue engaging these audiences will be intensified in the coming months through activities such as the promotion of the Winter School (WP5), feedback workshops related to the validation of the Social Network Analysis (SNA, under WP2), the Lund Conference in June 2026 (WP6), among other project activities. As more project outcomes become available and additional engagement activities are introduced in the coming months of the project, audiences currently involved to a lesser extent, such as policymakers, investors, living labs, will be increasingly targeted.

2.1 Messages

In the early stages of the project, communication and dissemination activities focused on general messages to raise awareness about FoSSNet. As the project progressed and specific activities were implemented, targeted messages about progress, results, and opportunities for engagement (e.g. FoSSNet conferences, surveys, etc.) have also started being disseminated.

These messages are continuously refined as needed, based on the actual experiences engaging these actors.

3 FoSSNet Vision & Mission

This chapter focuses on the project's vision and mission and the process followed to define these statements. The purpose of defining the FoSSNet vision and mission is to establish a common understanding of the project's direction, enabling clear, effective, and jargon-free communication to actors outside of the project.

During the first months of the project, partners contributed to defining the preliminary versions of the vision and mission statements. These early discussions, which took place during the in person KoM in April 2024, along with the feedback received during the

development of the initial communication and dissemination strategy, are described in detail in the DEC Plan (D6.1).

Following this initial phase, RUC and EUFIC facilitated a process to revisit and refine key FoSSNet concepts (e.g. food systems science, food systems transformation, among others) and the vision and mission statements. This included two collaborative online workshops with WP leaders and one consortium-wide online workshop. The aim of this process was to further explore the project’s conceptual foundations and ensure alignment across WPs.

- **Workshops with WP leaders (November 2024 – January 2025):** Two online workshops were held with WP leaders. The first, on 19 November 2024, discussed key FoSSNet concepts and the project's vision and mission. A Miro board was used to guide the process through a four- step exercise: goals → strategy/operational → outputs → impact. This activity helped rethink and refine the draft statements presented in D6.1.

The second workshop, held on 10 January 2025, focused on achieving internal alignment. These discussions served as the basis for the consortium’s online meeting at the end of January.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Miro board used during the first workshop with WP leaders held in November 2024.

- **Consortium online meeting (28 January 2025):** This meeting served as a crucial moment where the entire consortium collectively reviewed and aligned on the shared concepts, vision, mission, and the project's external and internal communication strategy. The different versions of the vision and mission statements developed through the WP leader workshops were shared on a **Padlet board**, where all partners could vote and comment. Based on this, the most supported options were selected for final refinement by EUFIC.

Following this process, EUFIC started developing a dedicated section on the FoSSNet website to present the final vision and mission. However, the development of this content was temporarily paused to prioritise the planning and organisation of the FoSSNet Oxford Conference. This section is part of the upcoming broader website update, scheduled for launch in September 2025.

4 Dissemination and communication tools and activities

The achievement of the objectives of the DEC plan will be ensured by the complementarity of its activities and thanks to the use of different tools and channels aimed at addressing identified stakeholders' needs and expectations. This chapter describes the work carried out within Tasks 6.2, 6.3, and 6.4 up until this moment. The following tools and activities implemented are presented in detail:

- Brand identity
- FoSSNet website
- FoSSNet landing page on other platforms (EUFIC website, FOOD 2030 Online Platform)
- Social Networks (FoSSNet LinkedIn page, EUFIC channels, partners' channels)
- Promotional kit (roll-up banner, leaflet, and project standard presentation)
- Press Releases
- Lay articles
- Newsletters (SFSN newsletter, EUFIC newsletter, project newsletter)
- External dissemination activities for the FoSSNet project (networking activities, events and conferences)
- Other communication and dissemination materials and activities

4.1 FoSSNet logo & brand identity

The FoSSNet brand identity is based on recognizable elements (e.g. brand color, logo, name, symbol) that allow the target audience to easily identify the project. Therefore, the logo is one of the key elements of the project identity, which aims to effectively represent the vision, mission and core objectives of the FoSSNet project. As the project follows an inter- and transdisciplinary approach, the logo and its key elements have been designed considering perspectives of the whole consortium, in a process coordinated by EUFIC.

At the very beginning of the project, EUFIC developed two options based on the opinions from all partners collected through a survey prior to the online KoM. These options were then presented during the online KoM and, after all partners voted on their preferred option with further comments for improvement, the final logo version was selected:

Figure 2: Final version of selected logo.

EUFIC's graphic design team has created a brand manual to guide partners and external users (e.g. web developers) in the correct use of the logo and its elements. All partners were encouraged to use the brand manual, which is accessible on the internal project SharePoint platform. The manual shows the different versions of the logo, the specific font, colors and dimensions, as well as examples of the logo's application on different materials.

Additionally, EUFIC designed project templates and encouraged all partners to use them in both internal and external communications about the project. These include a Word template and a PowerPoint template. A dedicated template for project deliverables has also been developed and shared among partners to ensure consistent reporting of the project's progress. Finally, a letterhead and various backgrounds for virtual meetings have been produced and shared with all project partners.

Figure 3: Cover slide of the PowerPoint template.

Figure 4: Example of a FoSSNet virtual background.

4.2 FoSSNet website

The website is the entry point and the primary information source of the FoSSNet project, informing about its scopes, activities, partners, news, events and results, and it is connected to the project's channels and media (i.e. FoSSNet LinkedIn page, SciFoodHealth social media accounts, and SFSN). It has been registered at: <http://fossnet.eu>. Deliverable 6.1 provides detailed information on the website development and structure. The FoSSNet website (Deliverable 6.2) was launched on Month 5 (June 2024). Since the website went live, it has achieved 8393 pageviews, 3621 visits from users from 79 distinct countries, and the average time visitors spend on the website is 2 minutes and 46 seconds (reference period: from 26 June 2024 to 15 July 2025; statistics collected via Matomo).

Website content is prepared with the contribution of all partners. EUFIC is responsible for the last fine-tuning of the texts provided and for their uploading on the website. Moreover, EUFIC continuously updates and improves the project website with news, events, resources (including public project deliverables and milestones), and lay-out adjustments to make the website more user-friendly. Among others, pages for the FoSSNet Oxford Conference have been added. A more extensive website update is currently being prepared, which includes the introduction of new project-branded

visuals and webpages, such as those on the project’s vision and mission, the Lund Conference, Winter School, and the SNA validation workshop. The updated website will be launched in early September 2025.

Partners are encouraged to share and use the project website in their institutions, companies, and scientific project pages on social media accounts.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the FoSSNet website – [News page](#).

4.3 FoSSNet landing page on other platforms

To help drive traffic to the FoSSNet website, dedicated webpages about the project have been integrated into external websites.

A specific page outlining the objectives, expected outputs, and contact information for FoSSNet has been created on [EUFIC’s website](#), which currently receives over 2 million web visits annually.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the FoSSNet page on the EUFIC website.

As part of the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network, FoSSNet also has a dedicated page presenting the project and its core activities on the FOOD2030 Online Platform.

Figure 7: Screenshot of the FoSSNet page on the FOOD 2030 Online Platform.

4.4 Social Networks

Social media is a useful tool to raise public awareness about FoSSNet project, to share project developments and results, and to redirect traffic to the project website. To reach different target audiences and achieve wide dissemination, FoSSNet has been using multiple social media channels, including different LinkedIn pages and X.

All social media posts consistently include the project hashtag (#FoSSNet) for easy statistics tracking and link to the project website. Wherever possible, the posts invite users to subscribe to the project's newsletter.

4.4.1 FoSSNet LinkedIn page

The [FoSSNet LinkedIn page](#), launched in April 2024 and managed by EUFIC, has been the preferred and most used channel. It aims to be the dedicated space to share not only project-related information and updates but also to promote networking and conversations among the interested entities. Content from other projects (e.g., FOODPathS, CLEVERFOOD, FOSTER) that is relevant and related to the project's scope has also been shared on the FoSSNet LinkedIn page.

As of today (15 July 2025) the page has 521 followers and 42 posts shared. All project partners have been actively engaging and resharing the project contents on their institutional and personal social media accounts, greatly contributing to increase the project's reach.

Figure 8: Examples of LinkedIn posts on the FoSSNet page and partners' engagement.

4.4.2 SciFoodHealth LinkedIn and X

Capitalising on the established presence of the EUFIC-managed SciFoodHealth channels (LinkedIn and X accounts), with high visibility and current reach of >28.000 followers in total, including experts, researchers, scientists, and other stakeholders interested in food and health topics as well as EU research project outcomes, FoSSNet related content has also been shared through these channels.

Since the beginning of the project and the launch of the hashtag #FoSSNet, 10 posts related to FoSSNet have been published on @SciFoodHealth.

Figure 9: Examples of LinkedIn and X posts from SciFoodHealth account.

4.5 FoSSNet promotional kit

To support the dissemination and communication of the project and provide audiences with an overview of the FoSSNet main objectives, approach and activities, a promotional kit was created at the early stage of the project. The kit consists of a roll-up banner, a leaflet, and a general presentation of the project.

According to the DEC Plan (D6.1), factsheets are also planned as part of the promotional kit. Up to this point in the project, partners have not expressed a need to develop this type of material. However, as results are becoming available, their development will start soon. WP leaders and partners are responsible for the text draft definition, while EUFIC develops the graphic design.

4.5.1 Roll-up banner

To increase the visibility of the project, a roll-up banner was developed and distributed among project partners. The roll-up has been mostly used in events (e.g. FoSSNet Oxford Conference, external events with exhibition spaces) and in person activities organised by the project (e.g. territorial labs workshops). When needed and upon partners' request, the roll-up has also been translated into local languages (e.g., Latvian).

Figure 10: FoSSNet roll-up banner in English and in Latvian.

4.5.2 Leaflet

The first leaflet was designed to explain the main project purposes and present FoSSNet's approach. It was printed and distributed during events, but also shared online [here](#).

An updated version of the leaflet is currently being prepared to reflect the project's evolving narrative and messages, vision and mission. Additional leaflets will be produced according to the WP leaders' requests and needs, mainly to engage specific target audiences. These will be disseminated during events, via social media and newsletters, and will also be made available in a digital version on the FoSSNet website.

Figure 11: FoSSNet leaflet (version from the early-stage promotional toolkit).

4.5.3 Project standard presentation

All FoSSNet partners are encouraged to present the project, their activities and results in seminars, public hearings, meetings, conferences and other relevant events, with the objectives to inform the target audiences and engage them, promote the project activities and their exploitation, contribute to the establishment of collaborations. Considering this, a standard presentation of the project was prepared by EUFIC with contributions from WPs. This presentation is currently being updated with visual elements and adapted content to better reflect the developments and preliminary results achieved so far.

4.6 Press Releases

Press releases are being developed to raise awareness and inform the media about the project's main activities, developments and results. Thanks to this tool, more stakeholders are expected to be reached.

As stated in the DEC Plan (D6.1), EUFIC is responsible for composing the first draft version in English of each press release, which is then shared with the coordinator and other relevant partners (i.e., the WP responsible for the activities presented in the press release). When ready, the press release is sent by EUFIC to journalists and media representatives selected according to their relevance to the topic, as well as via the media platform [AlphaGalileo](#). Moreover, the document is shared with all partners, inviting them to send it to their contacts through their press offices and conducting a translation, if required. Finally, press releases are made available on the project website and promoted on social media.

The first press release was shared in Month 4 (May 2024), providing an overview of the project's activities, ambition, and its relevance within the context of Europe Day celebrations (9 May). It was sent to 26 journalists and media representatives across Europe from EUFIC's media contacts and uploaded to AlphaGalileo. It was then published on the FoSSNet website ([here](#)) and shared as an article on the project's [LinkedIn page](#). This press release was also translated into Danish by RUC partners and distributed among Danish media contacts.

The press release received 611 hits on AlphaGalileo (i.e. number of times it was read).

Additionally, the press release was picked up by the Funding News Editor at Science | Business (<https://sciencebusiness.net/>) who asked to arrange an interview with project partners. An online interview with the FoSSNet coordinator and co-coordinator took place on 23 May 2024.

At the date of this deliverable, a second press release, focusing on the outcomes of the FoSSNet Oxford Conference and the public announcement of next year's Conference in Lund, is being produced. It is planned to be finalised and released by the end of July 2025.

4.7 Lay articles

Short articles in simple and non-technical language are being developed. These articles are aimed at non-academic audiences interested in the topic of food systems and are meant to help understand the project's work and approach. In addition, these articles facilitate non-academic audiences' engagement with FoSSNet, increase the project's outreach and raise awareness on food systems transformation. The articles will be made available on the project's website and promoted through social networks.

Compared to the timeline indicated in the DEC Plan (D6.1), this activity started slightly later than originally planned. As part of the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) "Unpacking food systems" campaign during May – July 2025, three short articles were produced. This campaign was seen as a relevant and valuable opportunity to kick off the article development process. Given their short format, they are currently being further elaborated to include recent project outcomes, such as the updated conceptual framework, and will be republished on the FoSSNet website and further promoted. These initial articles cover the following topics:

- Representing food systems: frameworks and elements
- How to accelerate food systems transformation: perspectives from funded projects (in collaboration with FOODPathS and CLEVERFOOD)
- Inclusion for food systems transformation: a look at early-career engagement

Screenshots of these three articles can be found in Appendix II.

Over the course of the project, more articles will be developed with contributions from partners, including the Diverse Early Career group, and following different formats (e.g. interviews with project partners, summaries of deliverables, understanding food system concepts, etc.). EUFIC, in collaboration with partners, will also explore opportunities to publish these articles on external platforms beyond the FoSSNet and partner organisations' websites in order to amplify the project's reach.

4.8 Newsletters

4.8.1 FoSSNet project newsletter

To further improve the dissemination of FoSSNet project activities, a dedicated e-newsletter was initiated by EUFIC. Although this activity was not part of the initial

communication and dissemination strategy outlined in D6.1, it was identified, together with partners, as a valuable tool for engaging the existing FoSSNet community, facilitate communication within the network, and attracting newcomers.

The newsletter highlights project activities and updates, events, and the most recent dissemination materials. It is distributed via Brevo to a growing list of subscribers and promoted via the project website, social media, and registration forms used for project events (e.g., the FoSSNet Oxford Conference registration form). As of July 2025, the newsletter list contains 190 subscribers.

EUFIC is responsible for designing the newsletter template and drafting the initial content based on key updates and activities mentioned by partners. The draft version is then reviewed by the coordination team.

The first issue was sent on 23 May 2025, sharing highlights and resources from the FoSSNet Oxford Conference and promoting the project's surveys. It was made publicly available through the project's website (in the resources webpage [here](#)) and the LinkedIn page. Two more issues are planned for 2025: one in September and another in December.

The newsletter is planned to be released quarterly, with a total of three issues per year.

Figure 12: First page of the project newsletter sent on 23 May 2025.

4.8.2 Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) newsletter

FoSSNet is actively using SFSN to promote project activities and engage with its community of more than 2700 stakeholders working in food systems, not only through feed posts and events, but also by featuring FoSSNet in its internal newsletters.

As mentioned above in the section related to the lay articles, from May to July 2025, FoSSNet participated in the newsletter campaign “Unpacking Food Systems”. The short articles developed for this purpose reached 2669 recipients on 8 May 2025, 2682 recipients on 26 May, and 2720 recipients on 10 July (data of the newsletter issues that included the FoSSNet short articles).

In addition to the short articles, posts shared in the main SFSN group feed, such as the posts announcing the FoSSNet Oxford Conference and calls for collaboration in the project's survey, were also highlighted in previous issues of the SFSN newsletter, reaching more than 2600 stakeholders.

4.8.3 EUFIC Members newsletter

EUFIC has leveraged its own established channels for broader dissemination. FoSSNet news have been regularly featured in EUFIC newsletters sent to members (>120 recipients), including announcements about the project start (February 2024), LinkedIn page launch (April 2024), website launch (August 2024), and the FoSSNet Oxford Conference (February 2025). EUFIC members include universities, research institutes, professional organisations and other non-profits, making them highly relevant audiences for the project. Therefore, the EUFIC team will continue to feature FoSSNet news in future issues to promote the network and encourage new organisations to get involved in the project's activities.

4.9 External dissemination activities for the FoSSNet project

4.9.1 Networking activities

As mentioned in D6.1, EUFIC, supported by partners (particularly WP2), will develop a catalogue with potential synergies for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, and other potential collaboration with and between stakeholders, projects, initiatives, and networks.

Initial steps were taken in December 2024 with the creation of the 'FoSSNet surveys contacts and communication tracker'. This Excel file, developed by EUFIC as a request from the coordination team and partners leading survey activities (specifically WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5), was designed to monitor contacts and communication efforts related to external synergies and surveys.

The tracker will serve as the basis for the synergies catalogue. Contact details (only strictly necessary personal information) from external stakeholders met in other project activities, such as participation in the FoSSNet Oxford Conference, or of whose email

contacts are publicly available, have been added to the tracker. In addition, the tracker includes individuals who autonomously subscribed to the project newsletter, where they expressed interest and consented to receive project-related updates. During the coming months, EUFIC, in close collaboration with Wageningen Research, will further develop this file and set a concrete procedure to streamline outreach towards external stakeholders.

To support this, it was decided that EUFIC will create a registration form to be used (and adapted when needed) across all project activities, along with a set of accompanying guidelines for all project partners. This will include the development of a Word document template and a Microsoft Forms template, both incorporating the FoSSNet branding, privacy policy, and a field for newsletter subscription. These materials will be developed to ensure full compliance with GDPR requirements and will be made available in the next couple of months on the project SharePoint.

Since the early stages of the project, several collaborative communication and networking opportunities have been identified. These efforts have been implemented through project presentations, participation in events and conferences, and individual contacts made by partners. Exchanges with other projects and networks have already resulted in some collaborations, including:

- In February 2024, FoSSNet joined the [FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network](#) (established and managed by the CLEVERFOOD project), becoming part of a community of more than 90 EU-funded projects working on food systems. Since then, EUFIC has maintained regular contact with the FOOD 2030 Networks' communications team and FoSSNet contents have been shared on their channels (FOOD 2030 Networks LinkedIn page and FOOD 2030 Online Platform).
- In March 2024, a meeting was held between EUFIC, EFFoST and FOODPathS partners to explore potential collaborations, particularly related to the Network of Universities on Sustainable Food Systems.
- In May 2024, EUFIC included FoSSNet in its projects catalogue for members, distributed to over 80 contacts. FoSSNet was also presented during EUFIC members meetings in June 2024 (30 attendees) and again in June 2025 (35 attendees), engaging attendees with the FoSSNet network.
- In October 2024, FoSSNet participated in the "Fair Food Revolution" campaign for World Food Day, organised by CLEVERFOOD and FOOD 2030 Networks.
- The CLEVERFOOD and FOOD 2030 Networks coordinator was invited to participate in the first FoSSNet conference in Oxford (25-27 March 2025), along with representatives from other projects including FEAST, FoodClic, FOSTER, FOODPathS and PLAN'EAT.

- In May 2025, FoSSNet leaflets were distributed during the FOODPathS Festival (20-22 May, in Brussels), and the poster produced by the Wageningen Research team about the social network analysis results was displayed in the exhibition space.
- Following discussions regarding the Higher Education Institutions Network, the planning of a joint online event between FoSSNet, CLEVERFOOD, FoodClic and FOODPathS, has been initiated by partners from VU Amsterdam. This event is scheduled for September 2025. EUFIC will provide relevant technical assistance and visual materials.

4.9.2 Conferences and events

External events and conferences provide an opportunity to present FoSSNet, share its results and engage new potential stakeholders. FoSSNet partners have been actively participating in different types of events, from workshops and meetings to larger-scale conferences, both online and in person, with different aims and audiences. To date, FoSSNet has participated in 29 conferences and events, addressing more than 2000 people.

An initial list of relevant national and international events was included in D6.1. A dedicated tab in the '*Reporting Communication and Dissemination activities*' spreadsheet (available on the project SharePoint) was added, and it will be regularly updated in collaboration with all partners. EUFIC will send reminders at least every three months integrated into the internal newsletter (described in chapter 6) to encourage all partners to help populate the list by identifying potential events of interest to represent FoSSNet.

As part of Task 6.4, FoSSNet will organise three interlinked conferences during the project's lifetime and an additional event will be held in Warsaw, focusing on expanding the network in Eastern Europe. These events will serve as a forum for sharing knowledge and ideas, empowering all stakeholders, and contributing to the achievement of the project objectives.

The first conference took place in Oxford from 25 to 27 March 2025. This document specifically highlights the communication and dissemination materials produced for the FoSSNet Oxford Conference. These include pre-, during and post-event materials, namely:

- Save the date banner (social media)
- Email signature

- Webpage for invitees and a 3-page PDF document to accompany the invitations
- Branded registration forms
- Event programme template
- Badges template
- Poster template
- Canvas for the online sessions
- PowerPoint template
- Speaker visuals for social media
- Webpage with the highlights, presentation slides, and session recordings (available on the SciFoodHealth YouTube channel)

FoSSNet Oxford Conference 2025

Resources & Highlights

Welcome to the official resource hub for the First European Food Systems Science Conference "Food Systems Science: Establishing a Common Framework and Networks" held in Oxford, UK on the 25th - 27th March 2025.

On this page, you'll find all the key materials from the event, including speakers' bios and presentations, session recordings, breakout group activities materials, and key takeaways. Whether you attended live or are catching up after, this collection is designed to support ongoing collaboration and knowledge sharing.

Scroll down to explore the full conference, day by day - or jump straight to a session:

- **Session 1:** Defining Food Systems and Food Systems Science
- **Session 2:** Assessing the State of Food Systems Science
- **Session 3:** Food Systems Science in Food Systems Transformation
- **Session 4:** Strategising the actions to establish the Food Systems Science Network and mobilise its members

Before you dive into the sessions, take a minute to meet our speakers

[Meet our speakers](#)

Figure 13: Examples of the materials developed for the FoSSNet Oxford Conference.

EUFIC was responsible for the graphic design, while all partners, especially the ones involved in the conference organisation committee, contributed to the conceptualization by providing content and feedback on the materials. Additionally, FoSSNet partners supported promotion by sharing the materials with their own contacts/networks via their personal and/or institutional social media channels.

The FoSSNet Oxford Conference provided both formal and informal networking opportunities for participants. In addition to the plenary sessions, the programme included breakout group sessions that allowed participants to engage in discussions, exchange ideas, and gain a deeper understanding of each other's professional work and interests. Two of these breakout sessions were also accessible online, with the goal of involving additional stakeholders, particularly early career researchers and professionals, in the project and the broader FoSSNet community. Lunch and dinner were included in the programme each day to encourage informal networking.

All aspects and processes related to the planning, organisation, execution, and post event follow-up will be further detailed in a dedicated deliverable (D6.4) due in M24 (January 2026).

At the time of this deliverable, planning for the 2026 Lund Conference is underway. Promotional materials are being developed, including the conference logo, save-the-date visuals, and a dedicated webpage.

4.10 Communities of stakeholders

4.10.1 Sustainable Food Systems Network

As part of the initial communication and dissemination strategy outlined in D6.1, the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) was identified as a valuable tool to connect and engage a broad online community of >2700 members. These members represent policymakers, entrepreneurs, researchers, NGO representatives, citizens, students, and others interested in being engaged in food systems. In the case of FoSSNet, it is an ideal platform to find and understand the interest of our target audiences, and it is necessary to promote activities in the network that include them, such as workshops where everyone participates and feels part of the "network" and can give their opinion.

The objective of having selected SFSN as a channel is to continue building a network that can provide direct feedback and can benefit and help to shape food systems science taking into consideration the views of all the disciplines involved in it.

This approach is still valid, as SFSN has proven to be an effective channel for promoting FoSSNet activities, generating interest and engagement from external stakeholders.

Although only a limited number of FoSSNet-related posts and events have been published on SFSN (9 in total so far), the community has responded to the opportunities posted, particularly those related to the FoSSNet Oxford Conference. A call for projects from the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network to showcase their work at the conference through a poster was shared in the ‘Communication, Dissemination and Mass mobilization’ subgroup, whose members are mainly professionals involved in the communication and dissemination activities of projects. As a result, the FEAST team expressed their interest in showcasing their project poster, and the FEAST coordinator was invited to pitch the project in one of the conference sessions. An event was also created for the online sessions which led to a significant increase in the number of registrations.

Additionally, as described in the ‘Newsletters’ section above, content shared via the SFSN newsletter also demonstrated a broad reach.

FoSSNet will continue to use SFSN not only to promote the project but, more importantly, to share opportunities for collaboration and extend invitations to participate in project events, such as the FoSSNet Conferences.

Figure 14: Example of posts and events published on SFSN.

4.11 Other communication and dissemination activities

In addition to the communication and dissemination activities described in the sections above, other actions outlined in D6.1 have not yet been implemented but are planned for the next phase of the project. As project results become available, additional activities targeting specific audiences, will be developed. These upcoming activities include scientific articles, practice abstracts, and policy briefs (please refer to D6.1 for the complete description of each activity).

Furthermore, planned initiatives such as podcasts and posts on external platforms will be supported by the well-established channels of FoSSNet partners, particularly EIT Food, through the EIT Food podcast channel and the EIT FoodHive platform.

Additional activities suggested by partners, such as short videos and webinars, seen as relevant not only for reaching and engaging external stakeholders but also for collaborating with other projects and initiatives and promoting the FoSSNet network, are being considered.

5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were fixed to assess the implementation of the DEC plan every 12 months. In addition to the evaluation, KPIs will enable partners to correct and re-address the strategy, considering also new emerging needs, external factors affecting the project and experience gained by the FoSSNet consortium in implementing the planned activities. KPIs are established considering the ones contained in the Grant Agreement and new ones introduced in the first months of the project. An overview of the status of the communication and dissemination tools, channels, and activities is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of Key Performance Indicator per communication & dissemination activity

Tools, channel activities	Metrics method	Expected results (KPI) by the end of the project	Results by July 2025	Status	Comments
Website	Number of website views and countries reached	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total page views: >15.000 - Countries reached: >20 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3621 visitors (average time spent on the website: 2,46 min) - 79 countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slightly below expectations (but not problematic) - Achieved 	As the project progresses, more outcomes become available and activities take place, additional content will be added to the website and promoted. Therefore, this number is expected to increase in the coming months of the project.
Social Networks	Number of posts, impressions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of posts: >120 - An average total reach of >10.000 impressions in the FoSSNet LinkedIn page and the SciFoodHealth accounts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 52 - 18.621 impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On track - Achieved 	
FoSSNet promotional kit	Number of kits and downloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotional kits produced: >1 - >500 downloads in total 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 - Not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On track 	As mentioned in the previous chapters, the promotional kit will be updated and the new version will be made available for download. For the early-stage promotional kit, the leaflet was mainly distributed in the printed version.

<p>Press Releases</p>	<p>Number of press releases, journalists contacted and downloads</p>	<p>- No. of press releases distributed: at least 3</p> <p>- No. of journalists contacted (direct email): >100</p> <p>- Downloads: >50</p>	<p>- PR #1 sent</p> <p>- 26 journalists contacted (European level)</p> <p>- 611 reads + 23 downloads (AlphaGalileo)</p>	<p>- On track</p> <p>- On track</p> <p>- On track</p>	<p>The first press release was transformed into an article for the website; therefore, the number of downloads in this particular case is based on the download metrics from the AlphaGalileo platform.</p>
<p>SFSN</p>	<p>Number of posts and news in the newsletter</p>	<p>- No. of posts: >15</p> <p>- News in the newsletter: >40</p>	<p>- 9</p> <p>- 4</p>	<p>- On track</p> <p>- Below expectations</p>	<p>Posts can be searched using the #FoSSNet hashtag in the SFSN. The number of news in the SFSN newsletter may be below expectations; however, this is not considered problematic as FoSSNet-related news have been included in other types of newsletters, such as the EUFIC members newsletter (4) and the Project newsletter (1st sent in May 2025 - not planned in D6.1)</p>
<p>Project Newsletter</p>	<p>Number of newsletters sent</p>	<p>- 3 newsletter per year</p>	<p>- Y1: 1 newsletter sent</p>	<p>- On track</p>	<p>New KPI</p>
<p>Lay articles</p>	<p>Number of articles produced and published on FoSSNet and partners websites</p>	<p>- No. of lay articles: at least 15</p>	<p>- 3</p>	<p>- Below expectations</p>	<p>This activity started later than initially planned but is expected to increase as plans to produce new articles have already been developed.</p>
<p>Liaison with networks, projects & initiatives</p>	<p>Number of activities implemented and actors engaged</p>	<p>- Collaborations established with No. projects & initiatives: >30</p>	<p>- 18 networking activities (1:1 meetings, joint comms activities, etc.)</p>	<p>- On track</p>	<p>Among others, FoSSNet is collaborating with CLEVERFOOD/FOOD 2030 Networks, FOODClic, FOSTER, FOODPathS, FutureFoods</p>

Conferences and events	Number of project presentations given by partners at local/ national/ EU/international events	- FoSSNet presentation in external conferences and events: at least 20	- 14	- On track	As mentioned, FoSSNet partners have attended 29 events so far. However, not all of these included a formal presentation of the project as part of the event programme. In some cases, the purpose of participation was to network, learn from other relevant initiatives, and explore potential collaborations.
Scientific articles	Number of scientific articles submitted or published by one or several partners	- No. of articles submitted: >15	-	- Not started	This activity is expected to take place more toward the second half of the project
Practice abstracts	Number of practice abstracts produced and uploaded to the EIP-AGRI portal	- No. of practice abstracts: >12	-	- Not started	This activity is expected to take place more toward the second half of the project
Policy briefs	Number of policy briefs produced and published on FoSSNet website	- No. of policy briefs released: >11	-	- Not started	This activity is expected to take place more toward the second half of the project
EIT FoodHive	Number of posts	- No. of posts: >45	-	- Not started	
Podcasts in the EIT Food channel and transcribed into articles	Number of episodes and listeners (per episode)	- No. of episodes made available: >3 - No. of listeners: at least 100	-	- Not started	

6 FoSSNet management structure and procedures - updates

During the first period of the project, the management structure and operational processes related to communication, dissemination, and networking activities were in line with the ones described in D6.1.

Besides the processes already in place, a few changes have recently been introduced to improve the overall coordination of these activities and to enable closer, more frequent exchanges with all project partners. The following paragraphs describe the new processes.

During the last consortium online meeting in January 2025, EUFIC proposed the idea of starting an **internal newsletter** as a way of keeping all consortium partners informed about project activities, considering the different timings of each task. The proposal was well received, and in agreement with the coordination team, it was decided that the newsletter will be implemented starting from the second semester of 2025 and circulated every three months. The proposed structure of the internal newsletter includes:

- A brief update from each WP, including links to relevant materials;
- A reminder about the reporting scheme available on the FoSSNet SharePoint (*'Reporting communication and dissemination activities'*);
- Highlights of upcoming events of interest for the project (e.g. opportunities to organise a session, present a project poster, or collaborate with other projects and initiatives), along with a request for partners' collaboration in identifying future events for FoSSNet participation.

The newsletter is intended to be a quick yet informative read, providing the most relevant information from each WP. It also aims to help identify potential content that could be further disseminated beyond the project consortium. EUFIC will be responsible for gathering the necessary inputs from partners, refining the content, and circulating the newsletter.

In addition to the internal newsletter, the consortium also agreed to try out a more casual and regular format for project-wide discussions: the **FoSSNet monthly café meeting**. As a first trial, these will be 30-minute online meetings held once a month and

open to all partners on a voluntary basis. The café meetings will serve as an opportunity for partners to connect with colleagues who may not be directly involved in the same activities or work packages, share updates, or request support. EUFIC is currently drafting a structure and facilitation method for these meetings, which will be finalised in collaboration with the coordination team. The first FoSSNet monthly café meeting is scheduled to start after the summer break. EUFIC will circulate the online invitations to the consortium. If considered valuable, the format and duration of these meetings can be adapted in the future.

7 Conclusions and next steps

This document has described the dissemination, communication, and networking activities carried out during the first period of the FoSSNet project in line with the strategy outlined in the DEC Plan (D6.1).

Throughout this phase, the communication and dissemination strategy has been adapted as needed by introducing new tools and adjusting timelines to better respond to emerging needs and opportunities. These changes reflect the project's ongoing commitment to strengthening both internal coordination and external outreach.

As the project enters its next phase, a key priority will be the development and dissemination of updated and refined materials that reflect current progress and effectively communicate project outcomes. These efforts will be crucial to increase stakeholder engagement, which plays a key role in supporting FoSSNet's goals and contributing to the creation of a robust FSS network.

Another important aspect will be the clear articulation of the network's value proposition. Communicating this effectively will help external stakeholders better understand the project's vision and mission and foster stronger collaboration.

Finally, a crucial opportunity to assess and further plan the upcoming activities will be the feedback and recommendations from the European Commission's independent reviewers, expected as part of the first interim evaluation report in October 2025. This will also guide the refinement of the communication and dissemination strategy moving forward.

Appendix I - Conferences & Events relevant for the project

An event calendar was created to identify the most relevant international days and events to promote FoSSNet materials.

Event name	Date	Location
European Research & Innovation Days 2025	16-17 September, 2025	Brussels, Belgium & Online
XXI European Rural Development Network Conference – <i>Food systems transition for sustainable rural development</i>	23-25 September, 2025	Bucharest, Romania
EAT Stockholm Food Forum 2025	3-4 October, 2025	Stockholm, Sweden
FAO Science and Innovation Forum 2025 – <i>Hand in Hand for Better Foods and Better Future</i>	13-17 October, 2025	Rome, Italy & Online
START Retreat for Young Researchers	28-29 October, 2025	Sønderborg, Denmark
39 th EFFoST International Conference 2025 - <i>Fostering the Transition to Sustainable Food Systems: Embracing Novelty and Overcoming Challenges</i>	17-19 November, 2025	Porto, Portugal
FOOD 2030 Networks Conference	2 December, 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark
Danish Presidency Conference – <i>Boosting and mainstreaming the bioeconomy – Science and governance for the green transition</i>	2 December, 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark
Danish Presidency Conference - <i>Transformative Governance for Food Systems and Biodiversity</i>	3 December, 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark

Appendix II – Short articles

Screenshots of the three short articles produced as part of the SFSN 'Unpacking food systems' campaign are available below.

1st article

(8 May 2025)

A SNEAK-PEEK INTO A EUROPEAN FOOD SYSTEMS FRAMEWORK

The **First Food Systems Science Conference**, held in Oxford in March 2025 and organised by the EU-funded project **Food Systems Science Network (FoSSNet)**, brought together researchers and practitioners to advance food systems thinking and science, and to clarify key concepts in the field.

One of the main focus was the **development of a food systems conceptual framework** (still a work in progress, you are getting a sneak peek!) focused on the European context. FoSSNet team reviewed 34 (!) existing frameworks, building on models from **Foresight4Food** and the **FAQ**.

The framework is being designed as a tool to help researchers, educators, policymakers, and communities **better understand the system**, define its key elements and boundaries, and **identify ways to change it for the better**. It will also support communication and a shared understanding across the project's work and broader community.

Food System Conceptual Framework for the FoSSNet Project (work in progress, version presented at the FoSSNet Oxford Conference, March 2025)

👉 If you are interested in joining the network or catching up on what was discussed, the session recordings and materials are available [here](#).

THE ART (AND CHALLENGES!) OF REPRESENTING FOOD SYSTEMS

In a world where an image is said to be worth a thousand words, **how we visually represent something as complex as the food system matters**. But representing food systems isn't as simple as drawing a few boxes and arrows. The challenge is not just showing the system; is helping people make sense of its dynamic and complex nature.

Diagramming a food system means wrestling with tough questions: where to draw the boundary between production and consumption, how to depict invisible power dynamics, and whether to include finance flows alongside nutrient cycles.

Even something that can be seen as a small **design choice**, like including a supermarket trolley illustration, can unintentionally reinforce an industrialised, consumer-driven model that doesn't reflect many local realities and contexts where food systems operate differently. And should the diagram be circular and interconnected to capture the complexity of the system, or simplified as a linear supply chain?

Finding the **balance between what can be included and what should be included** is an art in itself. The iterative process of inviting voices from ecology, economics, social justice and beyond ensures the final model doesn't flatten complexity, but rather guides users through it.

📖 WANT TO LEARN MORE? SOME SUGGESTIONS!

For a deeper analysis, check the following resources:

- 👉 Food systems [visual representations](#)
- 👉 Brief '[Understanding the food system: Why it matters for food policy?](#)'
- 👉 Primer on '[Demystifying Systems Thinking](#)'

2nd article 28 May 2025

HOW TO ACCELERATE FOOD SYSTEMS TRANSFORMATION?

👉 What is the biggest challenge in transforming Europe's food systems today?

The biggest challenge is that Europe's food systems are fragmented, meaning that different actors (like researchers, policymakers, and citizens) often work separately. These projects work toward a better future and here's how:

- FOODPathS is focusing on the disconnected governance structures
- CLEVERFOOD works to facilitate society-wide mobilisation
- FoSSNet is facing the siloed research efforts

Tackling complex food system goals requires integrated, inclusive approaches that bring diverse actors and knowledge together. A real team effort.

👉 What do these projects bring to the table that can help the transformation?

Each project adds a unique contribution: FOODPathS is creating a clear path and tools to help food system actors work together in partnership, CLEVERFOOD creates spaces for dialogue and local actions through labs and public engagement, and FoSSNet connects researchers across Europe to share knowledge and support better decisions.

👉 What kind of long-term change will these projects create?

The projects all aim to support deep, lasting change. FOODPathS wants to see an effective partnership that helps shape better food systems. CLEVERFOOD hopes for stronger, fairer food policies created with the public. FoSSNet wants research to be more connected, shared, and useful for real-world action.

👉 What would help these projects make a bigger impact?

To go further, all the projects need strong political support, stable funding, and policies that work together. FOODPathS and FoSSNet call for better research support and alignment, while CLEVERFOOD emphasizes citizen science and public engagement as drivers of change.

3rd article 10 July 2025

INCLUSION FOR FOOD SYSTEMS TRANSFORMATION: A LOOK AT EARLY-CAREER ENGAGEMENT

Inclusion is increasingly recognised as a key part of transforming food systems in a fair and sustainable way. But inclusion must move beyond theory. It needs to be embedded in governance, investment, and research, using diverse knowledge systems and disaggregated data to guide decisions.

This principle also applies to research and scientific collaboration. As part of the [FoSSNet project](#), a Social Network Analysis (SNA) was carried out to understand **how food systems researchers are connected in Europe, and how knowledge, resources, and influence flow** through these networks. SNA helps map these connections and identify gaps and opportunities for stronger collaboration.

One of the main barriers identified was the **limited role of early-career researchers** in the wider FoSSNet network. The analysis showed that these researchers tend to focus on their own work, collaborate mostly within their institutions, and have fewer types of connections.

What insights emerge when early-career researchers are given the space to speak? A session during the FoSSNet Conference in Oxford in March 2025 **gave them voice to reflect on the role of food systems science** in shaping a more ideal, just, and sustainable future. Here some of the key points they brought up:

- 👉 The importance of balancing top-down and bottom-up approaches.
- 👉 The value of local knowledge and agroecology, as well as the need to embrace interdisciplinarity and recognise diverse worldviews and knowledge systems, known as pluriversity.
- 👉 Growing importance of both AI technologies and local food systems, which are expected to evolve side by side.
- 👉 Context matters: solutions must be tailored to local realities, such as differences in meat consumption between regions.

